

Prevalence Of Lower Back Pain Among Tractor Driver – Observational Study

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ABSTRACT :

OBJECTIVE:To Determine Prevalence of lower back pain among tractor driver.

MATERIAL & METHODOLOGY:For the study, a sample of 100 students was selected, regardless of their age and gender. An observational study descriptive research design was used to collect data. In this case, the researchers collected data from around Amreli. To collect data, the researchers used a standardized, semi-structured questionnaire named the BPFS (back pain functional scale) and NPRS scale. This questionnaire consists of 12 questions, widely used to assess the lower back functional disability and pain among individuals. The questionnaire was distributed among the tractor drivers, and they were asked to fill it out honestly and without any external influence. Once the data was collected, it was analyzed using statistical methods to determine the prevalence of lower back pain among tractor drivers. The findings of the study were provided important insights of the low back pain status of tractor drivers.

INTRODUCTION : Low back pain is a common musculoskeletal symptom that may be either acute or chronic. It may be caused by a condition of diseases and disorders that affect the lumbar spine.^[1,2] Low back pain (LBP) is the most frequent work related musculoskeletal complaint and one of the leading causes of health related problems in developed world.^[3,4] Lower back pain is the leading cause of disability and inability to work and expected to affect up to 90 percentages of people at some point in their lives.^[5] Tractors are being extensively used as a source of on road transport in India. The vibration exposures among tractors are higher as compared to other on road vehicles.^[6] Work-related complaints are a major problem facing employees and employers, which have negative impact on their health and productivity. One of the most common work-related complaints is musculoskeletal symptoms which affect nearly a million workers each year in the United States according to the US Bureau of Labour Statistics and accounts for 85% of all workers' compensation claims.^[7] To find effective treatments is a challenge for medicine. Exercise and spinal manipulation are often recommended, yet their clinical effectiveness has not been documented beyond reasonable doubt.^[8] Back pain among older adults not only impacts quality of life but often leads to subsequent functional impairment and disability.^[9] Measured functional impairments also include self-reported difficulties with activities of daily living (ADLs) and documented muscle weakness including trunk extensor muscles, lack of flexibility, slow walking gait, and slower measured functional capabilities.^[10] Unlike younger adults, however, older adult back pain is less likely to be a

result of injury or overuse and is often complicated by multiple chronic conditions, degenerative disc conditions, poor mental and/or physical health, and other functional impairments.

METHOD : To collect data, the researchers used a standardized, semi-structured questionnaire named the BPFS (back pain functional scale) and NPRS scale. This questionnaire consists of 12 questions, widely used to assess the lower back functional disability and pain among individuals. The questionnaire was distributed among the tractor drivers, and they were asked to fill it out honestly and without any external influence. Once the data was collected, it was analyzed using statistical methods to determine the prevalence of lower back pain among tractor drivers. The findings of the study were provided important insights of the low back pain status of tractor drivers.

RESULT: Among the total 100 respondents the average age of respondent was 25-65 . I've conducted chi –square test among the two variables were BPFS scale and NPRS scale BPFS value is 49.5 and NPRS value is 37.4 . P-value is 0.001 is statistically significant . The percentage of scale indicate that BPFS is 60% and NPRS is 70%. The scores indicates that participants felt back pain during work .

DISCUSSION: This research aims to investigate the prevalence of lower back pain among tractor driver. The study utilized a observational study design, and data were collected using the BPFS questionnaire and NPRS. The study included 100 tractor driver in and around Amreli. The data analysis of NPRS revealed that among Tractor driver has average 1.47 score reported low back pain. The data analysis of BPFS revealed that among tractor driver has average 5.31 score reported low back pain. The data analysis BPFS revealed that among tractor driver, 60% reported low back pain. The data analysis NPRS revealed that among tractor driver , 70% reported low back pain. The results of the study showed that the prevalence of low back pain was high among in tractor driver . * 0 (0%) unable to perform any activity, 60 (100%) no difficulty in any activity. The high prevalence of low back pain among due to vibration and postural stress during driving .

CONCLUSION: After collection and analyzing the data which were collected from tractor driver was found that the maximum number of tractor driver is suffering from low back pain. Whereas the number of tractor driver has raised level of low back pain.

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